

Bobby Jackson (ANL)

*"I really enjoyed the IEA lidar side meeting last year. It was a great opportunity to **learn** about the latest developments in wind lidar technology and meet people working in this space."*

Griffin Modejski (UND)

*The Task 52 side meeting was a more intimate and collaborative setting to share ideas about how lidars can be implemented in the field in **novel ways** and about how the data can be processed and quality controlled.*

Alfredo Peña (DTU)

*"If we are calibrating cups and sonics with lidars, why are we not using lidars for all tasks involving the measurement of the flow in wind energy? Surely, the IEA task 52 needs to **help us in the further adoption of lidars** to the community"*

Storm Mata (MIT/NREL)

*"The biggest benefit for me was seeing what others were doing with respect to Task 52 and **meeting many of the people** whose work we relied on as a starting point."*

Pat Moriarty (NREL)

*"I really enjoyed **learning about challenges** of using lidar for wind energy applications and how these measurement systems are being used across the world to better understand wind farm performance."*

Norman Wildmann (DLR)

*"The Task 52 meeting at NASA was a great opportunity to present our recent lidar research, **get up to date** on advancements in the field and exchange ideas with industry and academia"*

Stefano Letizia (NREL)

*"It was great to find out how **lively, diverse, and visionary** the worldwide lidar research community is."*

Matteo Puccioni (LLNL)

*"IEA Task 52 provides the unique opportunity to **connect** research and industry at worldwide level."*

Sonia Wharton (LLNL)

*It was particularly helpful to **see what research Europe is doing** with scanning lidars at their wind park research sites and their newest ways to reduce error from volume averaging*

The US perspective

How are US national labs using lidars?

The US DOE strategy for field campaigns

Continental scale
Improve wind forecasting:

- On flat terrain, on mainland: **WFIP**
- On complex terrain, near the coast **WFIP2**
- Offshore: **WFIP3**
- On forest: **Tall Towers**

Wind farm scale
Improve understanding of interaction of wind plants with ABL: **AWAKEN**

Turbine scale
Improve understanding of interaction of turbulence with one big turbine: **RAAW**

Surfing USA: lidars on the WFIP3 barge

- One profiling lidar + two scanning lidars deployed for 3 months on an offshore barge
- Full wind profile + continuous vertical stares
- Combined with co-located measurements of temperature profiles: **first U.S. offshore measurement of wind and atmospheric stability**

Credit: Eve Cinquino, WHOI

WFIP3: adaptive scan scheduling with the WAGGLE node

Doppler lidar

Waggle node

Trigger 0.5° sector scan when 0-1 km max wind speed > 15 m/s and in southern cone

Go big or go home: the American WAKE experimeNT

Nacelle lidars
Detect inflow, wake deficit, meandering, speed-up/blockage (?)

Public data

Profiling lidars
Characterize ABL profiles, turbulence, PBLH, wind plant wakes

AWAKEN: yearly statistics from profiling lidars

AWAKEN: yearly statistics from nacelle lidars

AWAKEN: beyond lidars

THERMODYNAMIC PROFILING

CAN WAKE WARM UP THE SURFACE?

BORE DISRUPTS ABL STRATIFICATION

Do look up!: The Tall Turbines project

Tall Turbines: a complex experimental setup

ZX on 74-m tower over the trees

Daytime Convective Boundary Layer

Early Morning Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability

Lidars for all: standardizing and cleaning data with LiDARGO

This is an RHI scan...

...and this is what data looks like

CHECK IT OUT:
<https://github.com/NREL/FIEXTA/tree/main/lidargo>

Mind the gap: inpainting wind profiles with ML

Conditional diffusion model

Generative AI: creates new data based on patterns learned from existing (training) data

Forward (diffusion) process: adds noise to input data in a stepwise process until all information is lost. (No learning in this step)

Backward (denoising) process: Learn to remove noise in a stepwise process to generate new data

Conditioning: diffusion is conditioned on some amount of contextual information (a partial image in this case)

Diffusion models underlie common services like **Stable Diffusion** (Stability AI), **DALL-E** (OpenAI), and **Imagen** (Google)

The EU perspective

Old continent, new science: research testimonies from EU

U.S. DEPARTMENT
of **ENERGY**

Office of Energy Efficiency
and Renewable Energy

Testimony 1: the WIVALDI project

- 3 Windcube 200S
- Nacelle-based measurement
- Vertical profiling
- Cross-wake RHI
- Virtual towers with synchronized RHI

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→ Goal: setup a unique database of ABL, wake and WT data for research, development and validation

Testimony 2: DTU's future challenges

- Unbiased TI estimation from profiling lidars
 - Six-beam, Doppler spectrum info also for pulsed lidars
- Floating lidar TI overestimation
- Improve availability

Testimony 2: DTU's future challenges

- Better volume definition (frequency variations,...)
- Remote bias due to rain/assess rain from lidar
- Temperature lidar?
- Drone-mounted lidars?

Thanks all!

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